

QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART VII

BY T. N. GHOSH, S. L. LASKER AND S. BANERJEE

For pharmacological study against amoebiasis, 5-iodo-7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline, isomeric with Vioform, has been synthesised.

Recently 5-chloro-7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline ("Vioform") has been much used in the treatment of certain intestinal infections. The activity of the compound is believed to be due to the liberation of iodine in the intestine. But in case of prolonged administration there is a possibility of iodism and certain other physiological disorders. This liberation of iodine would undoubtedly depend on the stability of the iodo compound and this might vary with the position of the substituent in the benzene ring of the quinoline molecule. In "Vioform" iodine is attached to the 7 position and chlorine at the 5, the latter position being more reactive and stable. It has been considered to be of interest to study the characteristics of a quinoline compound which contains iodine at the 5 position and chlorine at the 7. It may be expected that such a compound would liberate iodine more slowly and as such may exert a more sustained therapeutic activity. With this idea in view 5-iodo-7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline has been prepared.

The action of iodine monochloride or chlorine on 8-hydroxyquinoline gives rise to 5:7-di-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline (Papesch and Burtner, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1314) or the corresponding 5:7-dichloro compound (*cf.* Lasker and Ghosh, *Science and Culture*, 1944, 10, 57). The constitution of the latter compound has been confirmed by its synthesis directly from 2-nitro-4:6-dichlorophenol by Skrap's reaction (*cf.* Brunner and Chuard, *Ber.*, 1885, 18, 445; 1896, 29, 708). It is, therefore, evident that halogenation of 8-hydroxyquinoline, under ordinary conditions, gives rise to 5:7-disubstituted derivative.

The action of iodine monochloride on the potassium salt of 8-hydroxyquinoline at 0° yields a mixture of 5-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline and the corresponding 5:7-di-iodo derivative. This mono-iodo derivative, on chlorination, yields 5-iodo-7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline, isomeric with "Vioform."

A certain comparative chemical test (*vide* experimental) indicates that the iodine atom in 5-iodo-7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline is more strongly bound than that in "Vioform."

E X P E R I M E N T A L

5:7-Dichloro-8-hydroxyquinoline.—(a) 8-Hydroxyquinoline (10 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (100 c.c.) and cooled in ice. Dry chlorine gas was passed into the solution till saturated, the colour of the solution changing to yellow. Alcohol was then distilled off on the water-bath and the residual solid was then thoroughly triturated with water and filtered. It crystallised from glacial acetic acid in colour-

less, slender needles, m.p. 178°-179°. (Found : N, 6·32. Calc for $C_8H_7ONCl_2$; N, 6·57 per cent).

(b) 2-Nitro-4 : 6 dichlorophenol (Ling, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1887, 51, 787 ; 25 g.) was mixed with dry glycerine (70 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (*d* 1·84, 30 g.) and the paste was heated carefully under reflux on a sand-bath under occasional shaking. When the reaction commenced, the sand-bath and burner were removed to avoid too vigorous a reaction. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool and concentrated sulphuric acid (30 g.) was further added. This mixture was heated carefully under reflux on the sand-bath for 4 hours and allowed to cool.

The dark mass was extracted with warm water and after filtration, the clear aqueous solution was treated with excess of sodium carbonate, when a solid (8 g.) was obtained which crystallised from glacial acetic acid (charcoal) in colourless, slender needles, m.p. 178°-179°. Its identity with the previous compound was established by mixed m.p. and analysis.

5-Iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline.—8-Hydroxyquinoline (14·5 g.) was dissolved in aqueous solution of caustic potash (5·6 g.). The aqueous solution was cooled to 0° and to this an alcoholic solution of iodine monochloride (16·2 g.), cooled to 0°, was gradually added under shaking. A light yellow solid was precipitated which was filtered and washed successively with aqueous solutions of sodium bisulphite, water, sodium thiosulphate and finally water.

The solid was next extracted with boiling alcohol and the insoluble portion, on crystallisation from glacial acetic acid, was proved to be 5 : 7-diodo-8-hydroxyquinoline (m.p. 200°-201°) by a mixed m.p. with a genuine sample, prepared according to the method of Papesch and Burtner (*loc. cit.*)

The clear alcoholic solution was diluted with large quantity of water, when a solid was precipitated which was extracted with ether. The ether solution on distillation, yielded a solid which was purified by solution in ether and distillation of the ether solution. The solid, thus obtained, was crystallised twice from boiling alcohol (charcoal) as a light yellow granular powder (2·5 g.), m.p. 123-24°. (Found : I, 47·01. C_8H_6ONI requires I, 46·86 per cent).

5-Iodo-7-chloro-8-hydroxyquinoline.—5-Iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline (8 g.) was dissolved in dry chloroform (150 c.c.) and cooled to 2°. Dry chlorine gas was then passed into this cooled solution till saturated. A solid was precipitated, which proved to be the hydrochloride of 5-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline. It dissolved in cold water and the base was precipitated on treatment with sodium carbonate.

The above chloroform solution, after filtration, yielded on distillation a solid which was washed with alcohol and was crystallised twice from glacial acetic acid (charcoal) in cream-coloured (with a yellowish tinge) slender needles, m.p. 147°-148° (deep red colouration), yield 3 g. (Found : Cl, 11·12 ; I, 40·89. $C_8H_5 ONCl I$ requires Cl, 11·63 ; I, 41·63 per cent). Iodine was estimated according to the method of Pearl (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1943, 148, 85) and chlorine was estimated by subtracting the corresponding iodine content from the total halogen content determined as silver halide.

When heated slightly with concentrated sulphuric acid, the above compound evolves copious vapour of iodine. Its alcoholic solution gives a deep green colouration with ferric chloride. It gives a green colouration with Million's reagent. When its solution in chloroform is shaken with 10 per cent nitric acid and the mixture allowed to stand for sometime, the chloroform acquires a violet-red colour and the nitric acid becomes somewhat yellow. Similar test with Vioform, under identical conditions, was done and it was found that the chloroform layer acquires the violet-red colour earlier than with the present compound, indicating that possibly the iodine atom in the present compound is more strongly bound than that in Vioform.

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BENGAL IMMUNITY RESEARCH LABORATORY,
CALCUTTA.

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QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES. PART VIII.

BY T. N. GHOSH, S. BANERJEE AND S. L. LASKER

By applying Skraup's reaction some hydroxyquinoline derivatives have been prepared directly from the corresponding nitro compounds.

In connection with some synthetic work, it was found necessary to prepare some chlorohydroxyquinoline derivatives. By following Skraup's method these quinoline derivatives have now been prepared directly from the corresponding nitro compounds. The application of Skraup's reaction in which the amine can be dispensed with and the corresponding nitro compound alone used with success is of interest both from the technical and theoretical point of view, the cost of reduction of the nitro compound being an important factor. Dey and Goswami (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 533) have converted nitrocoumarin into related quinolines without using amino coumarin.

The results obtained are summarised below :

Nitro compound (50 g.)	Quinoline derivative	Yield (uncrystallised)	M.p. (Crystallised)	Analysis	
				Found.	Calc.
(1) <i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	8-Hydroxyquinoline	5 g.	73-74°	N, 9.48	9.65%
(2) <i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	Nil	...	...	...	...
(3) 4-Chloro-2-nitro-phenol	5-Chloro-8-hydroxy-quinoline	18 g.	122°-123°	N, 7.61	7.82%
(4) 4 : 6-Dichloro-2-nitrophenol	5 : 7-Dichloro-8-hydroxyquinoline	16-18 g.	178°-179°	N, 6.84	6.67%
(5) 2-Chloro-4-nitro-phenol	5-Chloro-6-hydroxy-quinoline	14 g.	197°-198°	N, 7.69	7.83%